

Connected Open Source Software - ConnOSS

Project Proposals in the Area of Scientific Library Services and Information Systems (LIS)

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Abstract – English

Machine-actionable metadata for research artifacts is key to realize the FAIR Guiding Principles, contributing also to good practices as well as better quality and reproducibility. In addressing researchers developing research software, we identified that the majority would be interested in automated ways producing an overview on their software, increasing FAIRness without requiring much additional effort on their side. In recent years, the scientific community has turned to schema.org, a controlled vocabulary that makes it easier to provide FAIR descriptions of datasets, software and publications, among others. Efforts built on top of schema.org such as Codemeta, Bioschemas and the Machine-actionable Software Management Plan Metadata Schema aim to improve the metadata descriptions of research software. To make it easier for researchers, some efforts on (semi)automatic metadata extraction, mostly from GitHub, have emerged. However, none of the current efforts provide a high metadata coverage partially due to the multiple sources to be considered and harmonized. While there is some structured metadata available, e.g., from the GitHub API and citation files, there is a need to extend the metadata coverage with Machine Learning approaches using other sources (e.g., analyzing the README file). The Connected Open Source Software project (ConnOSS) will provide a GitHub/GitLab web pages infrastructure showcasing software production by research groups with consistent, harmonized, and enriched machine-actionable metadata; thus, improving the visibility and FAIRness of research software. In this way, it will make it easier for researchers to align to good practices and thus improve quality and reproducibility of research software, and for aggregators and registries to harvest high quality metadata, enabling the creation of, e.g., knowledge graphs. ConnOSS will build on top of existing approaches and will add a machine learning approach to enrich the metadata. It will also support researchers with the adoption tutorials and appropriate training. Furthermore, ConnOSS infrastructure and Machine Learning model, together with the extracted metadata will adhere to FAIR and open-access practices.

Abstract – German

Maschinell verwertbare Metadaten für Forschungsartefakte sind der Schlüssel zur Umsetzung der FAIR-Leitprinzipien und tragen zu Best Practices sowie zu erhöhter Qualität und Reproduzierbarkeit bei. Umfragen unter Wissenschaftler*innen, welche Forschungssoftware entwickeln, zeigen, dass die meisten von ihnen an automatisierten Verfahren zur Erstellung eines Überblicks über ihre Software interessiert wären, um die FAIRness zu erhöhen, allerdings ohne dass sie dafür viel zusätzlichen Aufwand betreiben müssten. In den letzten Jahren wird in der wissenschaftlichen Community viel schema.org eingesetzt, ein kontrolliertes Vokabular, das unter anderem die Beschreibung von Datensätzen, Software und Publikationen erlaubt. Auf schema.org aufbauende Projekte wie Codemeta, Bioschemas und Machine-actionable Software Management Plan zielen darauf ab, die Metadaten von Forschungssoftware zu verbessern. Momentan gibt zwar einige strukturierte Metadaten, z. B. aus der GitHub-API und Zitationsdateien, aber es besteht die Notwendigkeit, die Metadaten-Abdeckung mit Ansätzen des maschinellen Lernens unter Verwendung anderer Quellen zu erweitern (z. B. durch Analyse der jeweiligen README-Datei). Das Projekt Connected Open Source Software (ConnOSS) wird eine GitHub/GitLab-Webseiteninfrastruktur bereitstellen, die die Softwareproduktion von Forschungsgruppen mit konsistenten, harmonisierten und angereicherten maschinenverarbeitbaren Metadaten präsentiert und so die Sichtbarkeit und FAIRness von Forschungssoftware verbessert. ConnOSS zielt darauf ab, die FAIRness von Forschungssoftware zu verbessern, indem es eine GitHub/GitLab-Webseiteninfrastruktur mit konsistenten und harmonisierten angereicherten Metadaten über Gruppen und Organisationsrepositorien hinweg bereitstellt, die es Forscher*innen erleichtert, sich an Best Practices zu orientieren und so die Qualität und Reproduzierbarkeit von Forschungssoftware zu verbessern, und die es Aggregatoren ermöglicht, hochqualitative Metadaten zu sammeln und z.B. Wissensgraphen zu erstellen. ConnOSS wird auf bestehenden Ansätzen aufbauen und ein maschinelles Lernverfahren nutzen, um Metadaten anzureichern. Außerdem wird es Forscher*innen mit Tutorials und entsprechenden Schulungen bei der Einführung unterstützen. Darüber hinaus werden die ConnOSS-Infrastruktur und das Modell des maschinellen Lernens zusammen mit den extrahierten Metadaten den FAIR- und Open-Access-Praktiken entsprechen.

Background

Thanks to the publication of the FAIR Guiding Principles in 2016 [1] and their variations covering, e.g., research software (FAIR4RS) [2], computational workflows [3], and training materials [4], machine-actionable metadata for research artifacts has become more and more important in recent years, a trend that had already started for databases and datasets thanks to the Linked Open Data [5] initiative. While metadata helps us describe physical and digital objects even without access to the actual object, semantically structured machine-actionable metadata enables conceptual links across different (digital) objects, including but not limited to research artifacts. Schema.org [6] is a general-purpose controlled vocabulary providing a lightweight approach to semantically structured metadata that can be easily embedded on web pages but also provided as RDF, facilitating the creation of Knowledge Graphs [7]. It has been successfully used by scientific communities around Bioschemas [8], Science on Schema [9] and Data Discovery Engine [10].

Particularly for the case of research software, there are some schemas built on top of schema.org that have already gained some adoption and shown some benefits for the community. Codemeta [11] extends schema.org types to describe SoftwareSourceCode and SoftwareApplication and it has been integrated to the Software Heritage Archive [12] making it easier to get a common metadata layer for GitHub repositories; however, it is not yet exposed in a way that can be consumed in batch by machines. Codemeta compatible metadata can be automatically extracted with the tool Software Metadata Extraction (SOMEF) [13] with a coverage below 30% of the elements from Codemeta.

Bioschemas provides a recommendation, aka metadata profile, to use the schema.org description for SoftwareSourceCode. Bioschemas ComputationalTool profile has been integrated to Bio.tools, a software registry for life sciences related software. Web pages including ComputationalTool markup can be validated with FAIR-Checker [14] a FAIRness assessment tool that aligns to Bioschemas profiles. Thanks to the use of the ComputationalTool markup on web pages, aggregators could easily obtain the metadata and bring it together as, for instance, a knowledge graph. To the best of our knowledge, such an option has not yet been exploited. An analysis on a knowledge graph created from Dataset markup in the ELIXIR Plant Community on 2023 [15] showed some inconsistency on the way that the Bioschemas Dataset profile is used across institutes, making it difficult to get a coherent picture.

The Machine-actionable Software Management Plan metadata schema (maSMP) [16,17] builds on top of the SMP proposed by the ELIXIR Software Best Practices Focus Group [18] and aligns to the SMPs proposed by the eScience Center in the Netherlands [19] and the one by the Max Planck Digital Libraries [20]. maSMP extends schema.org types SoftwareSourceCode and SoftwareApplication, includes elements from Codemeta and Bioschemas, and proposes new elements to connect the software with its research management plan (and the corresponding Data Management Plan). The maSMP markup has been already adopted by the ELIXIR Software Management Wizard [21].

In addition to SOMEF, the Helmholtz Rich Metadata Software Publication (HERMES) [22] and the Software Metadata Synchronization (SOMESY) [23] also support metadata extraction. HERMES provides an automated workflow to publish research software in Zenodo with metadata extracted from the Citation CFF file [24], the CodeMeta JSON file and Git metadata. On its side, SOMESY keeps the metadata synchronized as it checks for metadata updates every time that files in the repository are modified.

Within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) scope, the Research Software Metadata working group [25] and the Base4NFDI project nfdi.software have already recognized the importance of metadata for research software and are currently analyzing the use of metadata by the consortia and commonalities across metadata schemas such as Codemeta, Bioschemas and maSMPs, among others. Furthermore, the maSMP metadata schema is planned to be integrated to the [Research Data Management Organiser](#) (RDMO), a management

tool with a growing number of users in Germany, as part of the efforts of different NFDI consortia.

Despite the efforts around metadata schemas and metadata extraction for research software, there is still room for improvement. With our ConnOSS project, we aim at providing a consistent and comprehensive metadata extraction and publication infrastructure that will serve humans and machines alike, so researchers and research groups can create a harmonized overview of their research software, making it easier for registries and aggregators to harvest the metadata and create additional value.

Use cases

We have identified three main use cases that ConnOSS would support: (i) providing researchers with a harmonized overview of their research software production, (ii) exposing machine-actionable research software metadata aligned to the FAIR for Research Software (FARI4RS) principles, and (iii) facilitating the consumption of such metadata by registries and aggregators. The need of an infrastructure as the one proposed with ConnOSS is supported by the state-of-the-art and the existing gaps regarding consistency and coherence on the provision, coverage, and exposure of research software metadata. Despite the importance of FAIRness, its adoption is not yet as broad as it should be as its implementation requires (additional) skills that are not necessarily common across all research domains. Therefore, there is a need for tools and infrastructure to make it easier for researchers to FAIRify their research artifacts.

Objectives

To support the three identified use cases, we have established the following objectives:

- Defining a metadata schema that combines and extends existing schemas
- Providing tools to extract machine-actionable metadata from existing sources
- Enriching the metadata with Machine Learning (ML) approaches
- Publishing the metadata for humans and machines alike

The figure below shows an overview of ConnOSS and its different components, which will be built on top of existing solutions to maximize compatibility and facilitate adoption. The access points refer to different ways for the users to interact with ConnOSS, the metadata extraction relies on direct sources such as data from the source code repositories but also from ML approaches, the metadata pages consist in the publication for humans and machines, and the metadata export makes it easy for registries and aggregators to harvest and consume the metadata. The metadata pages will rely on GitHub and GitLab web pages and will align to the FAIR Digital Object [26] effort to increase interoperability and reproducibility. To this end, we will use RO-Crates [27] and FAIR Signposting [28], two technologies fully aligned to web pages and used as an implementation of FDOs [29], known as webby FDOs.

Figure 1. Main components of ConnOSS as infrastructure.

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